

Targul Alizade

Lecturer, Baku Engineering University, Baku, Azerbaijan

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WORDS AND PHRASES RELATED TO BREXIT AS PERSUASIVE TOOLS IN BRITISH MEDIA DISCOURSE

Abstract.

One of the main reasons for the UK's exit from the EU was the persuasive strategies employed by the British media. The media utilized both persuasive and influencing tools. Both pro-Leave and pro-Remain newspapers played a key role as influencing agents. It is evident that the Leave campaign's slogan "Take back control" was more impactful than the Remain campaign's "Britain is stronger in Europe." The so-called "bombardment approach" became particularly prominent in the final stage of the campaign, especially in three of the five major tabloids: *Daily Mail*, *The Sun*, and *Daily Express*. Tabloids supporting the Leave campaign, which used strong and persuasive expressions, had significantly more readers than broadsheet newspapers. As a result, the tabloids' support for the Leave campaign played a decisive role in the campaign's outcome. Euroscepticism was one of the main rhetorical weapons of the British tabloids.

Keywords: Leave campaign, tabloids, pro-leave, pro-remain

Introduction. "The *Daily Mail*'s discourse on the EU was characterized by a world full of Franco-German plots, threats to Britain's sovereignty and security by an advancing European superstate, allegedly untrustworthy European partners and a preference for the USA over the EU." In this discourse, the so-called European superstate is portrayed as a threat to British sovereignty and security. The phrase "allegedly untrustworthy European partners" implies that other EU member states are unreliable. The newspaper also emphasized the superiority of the USA over the EU. In 2003, *The Daily Mail* described the draft EU constitution as a "blueprint for tyranny." In 2011, the paper claimed that Germany wanted to turn the EU into a Fourth Reich. Both *The Daily Mail* and *The Sun* often mocked and attacked the EU, displaying an antagonistic stance. (Gareth Harding, 2017)

After the referendum, *The Daily Mail*'s editor stated that supporting Brexit was "in the DNA" of the newspaper and its readers. Of the 25 headlines leading up to the referendum, 18 were directly related to it. Six of these headlines focused specifically on immigration. Another headline, similar to one in *The Express*, discussed pensions. In 2016, *The Daily Mail* warned pensioners in a headline titled "Why Staying In Europe Could Harm Your Pension" that remaining in the EU could lead to serious financial losses. Chancellor George Osborne claimed that a Remain vote could put pensions at risk. During a time of crisis in the Eurozone, the UK was expected to aid EU countries, and the article suggested this could lead to disasters. In contrast, the Leave campaign promised increased pensions through a stronger pound. (Daniel Martin, Dan Hyde, Ruth Lythe, 2016, p.12)

The official Leave campaign group *Vote Leave* was founded on October 15 and officially launched in April. It was backed by six key politicians, including then-London Mayor Boris Johnson and five other cabinet ministers. *Vote Leave* received support from various political parties, including the Conservatives and Labour. Another key development was the establishment of the *Leave.EU* group by businessman Arron

Banks in 2015. Banks, despite his earlier support for the Conservatives, donated €1 million to UKIP due to his animosity toward David Cameron. He also funded the Grassroots Out campaign. (Robert Booth, 2016)

Leave.EU claimed to represent the voice of the people and received broad public support. Initially called "The Know," the group included Nigel Farage and members of Grassroots Out. Formed in 2016, the movement sought to unite other Leave campaigns and held events across the country, attempting to reach 500 areas in a single day. According to the BBC, *Leave.EU* and *Grassroots Out* merged to protect the official "Out" campaign status and succeeded in uniting Leave supporters. The group rented a truck with the slogan "Say goodbye to Brussels" and parked it in front of the Electoral Commission building to attract attention. Regional leader Richard Murphy worked to make the slogan more memorable in public places. On the referendum day, the campaign ensured that all its members actively participated. (BBC News, 2016)

Vote Leave's arguments included stopping the £350 million weekly payment to the EU, protecting borders without EU oversight, curbing immigration, and establishing free trade deals with other countries. Among these, the promise to redirect £350 million to the NHS was one of the most influential, although later debunked by Full Fact. Boris Johnson admitted the UK never sent £350 million weekly to the EU and could never reclaim that amount.

At the time, a *Telegraph* correspondent reported Boris Johnson's claims that Brussels was interfering in UK affairs, aiming to undermine public trust in the EU Commission. *The Times* called for votes in favor of Eurosceptic leaders in the 1997 general election, framing the EU as Britain's main problem. Justice Secretary Michael Gove argued that leaving the EU would make Britain's borders safer and more controlled. *The Daily Mail* warned that continued integration with the EU could lead to a migration surge of 88 million.

"The only way we can stop our borders being lowered to allow millions more to be admitted, is to take back control and leave the European Union."

It claimed most migrants would come from poorer countries like Albania, then on track for EU membership. The article framed these refugees as security threats, particularly since Montenegro was associated with money laundering and drug trafficking: “They are serious criminals who came here on forged Italian and Greek documents.” The narrative suggests that stopping such individuals was a matter of national security. EU citizens moving undocumented across borders became a central argument for Brexit. (Michael Gove, 2016)

The Daily Express also played a distinctive role in Eurosceptic discourse. Under Richard Desmond since 2010, the paper launched the “Britain out of Europe” campaign, prominently featured on its front page, symbolizing the struggle to reclaim sovereignty. Nigel Farage, one of the biggest supporters of the Leave campaign, began writing for the newspaper in 2013 and became editor of UKIP media in 2014. The paper frequently criticized David Cameron and his support for Remain. In 2016, it published the headline “Cameron’s EU deal disaster, highlighting his failed negotiations. (Macer Hall, David Maddox, 2016)

The *Express* also gathered 370,000 petition signatures demanding a referendum on EU membership. Embracing the “bombardment approach,” the paper promoted Euroscepticism for years with billboard campaigns. Its anti-immigration and anti-EU stances had a major impact during the referendum campaign. Headlines like “EU very bad for pensions,” “Fury at PM’s EU pension threat,” and “New EU threat to your pension” illustrate how the EU’s influence was framed as a threat to retirees. The tabloids aimed to frighten and provoke older voters by suggesting rising taxes and unstable pensions.

Though known for economic reporting, the paper often featured pro-Brexit messages on its front pages. Examples include:

- “Queen Issues EU Challenge”
- “Huge Boost To EU Exit Hopes”
- “We Will Thrive Outside The EU”

These headlines used hyperbole and emotional appeals. They claimed that the Queen had endorsed Brexit and that the country had bright prospects outside the EU. On the day of the referendum, the headline read: “Your Country Needs You: Vote Leave Today,” appealing to patriotic sentiment. Another headline, “Outrage At Bid To ‘Rig’ EU Vote,” accused the government of extending the voting period to favor Remain. Ministers confirmed that traffic to the voting site had spiked.

“The more people who hear our message, the more who will want to leave,” claimed campaign chair Michael Gove, suggesting that support for Leave increased as the message spread. (Alison Little, 2016)

The Sun held a negative stance toward the EU between 1990–2000, with 80% of its editorial staff known as Eurosceptics. The paper propagated “euromyths” — falsehoods about the EU — prompting the European Commission to launch a fact-checking website. *The Sun* was a key backer of the Leave campaign, and while it did not cover the referendum as often as *The Daily Mail* or *The Express*, 12 of its headlines did focus on

the issue. Six of those were published in the campaign’s final nine days — strategically timed to influence last-minute decisions.

The headline “Fiend’s Euro Arsenal” referred to the EU as an evil force, presenting the euro as its weapon. As *The Guardian* noted, *The Sun*’s use of the phrase “blueprint for tyranny” exemplified the “power of print media” in shaping public opinion.

Statistical reports show that *The Times*, *The Sun*, and *The Daily Mail* emphasized immigration to instill fear. *The Sun* used headlines like “100 migrants an hour getting European passports” to provoke anxiety. *The Times* provided exact figures:

“Romanian and Bulgarians accounted for 58,000 of the net figure [of 333,000, total net migration to Britain in 2015], up from 44,000 in the previous year.”

The rise in Bulgarian migration was attributed to racist forces. Instead of addressing the causes of migration, the press focused on its growing scale. (Richard Ford, 2015)

Figures, metaphors, and other figurative language tools are able to convey fear and anger more effectively when used. *The Sun*, when presenting new arrivals, uses the phrase “invasion of the UK” and portrays Britain as the target of attacks, depicting migrants as brutal enemies. It compares migrants to natural disasters, describing the situation Britain faces as a “flood of 500k.” The hyperbolic metaphors “waves” and “flood” imply an uncontrollable movement and a loss of control. The phrase “take back control” is declared at this point as an urgent message of the Leave campaign. *The Sun* repeatedly dismisses accusations that its stance on migration is linked to racism, claiming instead that its position is not rooted in racism but in the belief that Britain cannot cope with these numbers. However much these ideas are instilled in readers, the main goal of the tabloids appears to be isolating migrants simply because they are different. Particularly, they expressed strong discomfort about an influx of Turks. The EU is portrayed as putting Britain at risk, emphasizing that Turkey, with its population of 80 million, could pose a threat to the UK if it became a member of the EU.

In *Daily Mail*, an article claims: “100,000 Turks would flock to Britain every year if the Muslim country became an EU member.” By presenting Turkey as a Muslim country, cultural and religious diversity is explicitly highlighted. Using such a large number as 100,000 amplifies the perceived scale of the threat.

Tabloids label suspicious Muslims as “Other” and use various Islamophobic rhetoric. While *The Sun* denies racism, it still publishes lines that incite it. Rather than improving public services and providing better care for these people, it argues that removing them would be more beneficial. However, pro-Remain newspapers strongly objected to these statements and so-called facts.

In her article “*Did the Mail and the Sun Help Swing the Vote towards Brexit?*” in *The Guardian*, Jane Martinson emphasizes the strong pro-Brexit stance of British tabloids, noting *The Sun*’s use of the Union Jack and slogans like “BeLeave in Britain” and later “See EU later.” She also examines *Daily Mail*’s phrase “If you believe in Britain, vote leave.” The paper strongly

criticizes Europe using phrases like “lies,” “greedy elites,” and “broken, dying Europe.” (Jane Martinson, 2016)

Such headlines aim not only to reveal the bitter truths of the referendum but also to emphasize the negative aspects of migration. Another headline depicts migrants inside a train from the Middle East with the caption “We are from Europe, let us in.” The article continues with “as politicians squabble over border controls,” blaming politicians due to ongoing disputes about border policies.

A headline in *Daily Mail* defends the necessity of stopping the illegal migrant influx, claiming this influx is caused by unnecessary EU decisions and laws.

The Guardian investigates the motives behind these positions. Editors of pro-Brexit newspapers, like many political leaders, justify their portrayal of migration by claiming Brexit is supported out of fear that a new power structure might emerge. When asked whether the British press has caused fear and anxiety over migrants for years, they defend themselves by saying they simply convey the truths the public has a legal right to know.

According to *BBC* reporter Daniel Sandford, the individuals shown in *The Guardian's* investigation were not from Europe, but from Iraq, intending to settle in Britain. This reveals how tabloids are not hesitant to use false or misleading stories to influence the public. Research shows that Britons trust newspapers more than European readers. Newspaper content often forms the basis for television news coverage as well.

Later, *Daily Mail* ran the headline “Who will speak for England?”, signaling the importance of independence and nationalism, and thus expressing support for the Leave campaign. While it doesn't exclude the views of ordinary people and the Eurosceptic British press regarding the consequences of Britain leaving the EU, it takes a clear stance. Although newspapers lost some prominence since the 1990s due to the rise of Facebook and Twitter, public trust in media sources has never been fully lost. The idea that reading habits have declined has never been accepted.

During the referendum, the Leave campaign's rhetoric served to direct the public. **SUN SAYS BACK BREXIT** “We urge you to make history and win back Britain's freedom... believe in yourself and our country's greatness – vote LEAVE

This is our LAST chance to remove ourselves from the undemocratic Brussels machine in the vote of a lifetime.”

The Sun, on election day, calls on Britain to make history and reclaim its freedom. Slogans like “Vote Leave” and “Believe in yourself and in the greatness of our country” are used. It describes Brexit as the last opportunity to escape the undemocratic Brussels machinery. Through imperative sentences like “We urge you” and “Sun says,” the article compels readers to support Brexit. Words like “Leave” and “Last,” in capital letters, are used to grab attention. The headline's phrase “Britain's resurgence” implies a revival and reawakening of the nation. (The Sun, 2016)

The *Daily Telegraph*, as Britain's most famous broadsheet, had a wide sphere of influence. Its claims

and ideas resonated strongly among the public. The paper published daily anti-EU stories, heavily loading readers with negative energy. Typical headlines included: “EU brainwash our children,” “Now EU Wants to Ban our Kettles,” and “Get Britain out of the EU.” These suggest “The EU is brainwashing the younger generation,” “exploiting our property,” and “Get Britain out of the EU.” Among these striking phrases is also “Euroscepticism,” meaning skepticism toward or opposition to the EU.

The Telegraph openly supported the Leave campaign, presenting political statements as evidence. For instance, it echoed Boris Johnson's speech, calling Brexit the only solution. In the headline, “Euroscepticism was in our DNA – How the Telegraph stood up to the establishment elite over three decades to push forward the views of the silent majority,” the paper claims it steered away from elite opinion and addressed the silenced majority. This elite group has always leaned toward Europe. The paper declares that Euroscepticism is embedded in its and others' genetic makeup. The elite has always played a crucial role in determining the fate of the people. (The Telegraph, 2016)

Even on election day, despite being a broadsheet, *The Telegraph* used striking language to express anti-EU sentiments, similar to tabloids. In the article “We must vote Leave to create a Britain fit for the future,” the serious paper calls for Leave support in order to prepare Britain for the future. It expresses support for adapting Britain to future developments, using the modal verb “must” to fulfill its persuasive function.

In the continuation of one article: “Tonight Britain departs from the EU, but, as Boris Johnson will tell the nation, this is not an end, it is a beginning. Mr Johnson recognizes that Brexit is a unique opportunity to rethink the way we do everything. Britain is taking back control, and once our lawmakers are fully in charge, there will be no one else to blame for error or inaction. The future will be in our hands.”

The paper, as in many articles, cites Boris Johnson and refers to the post-Brexit era as a “new beginning.” It views Brexit as the only way to think anew about the future. Once Britain takes back control, everything will change. The article stresses that decisions will be made by the people and executed by lawmakers, and it assures readers that no mistakes or inefficiencies will happen. It attempts to convince people that the future will be in their hands.

Conclusion. One of the key factors behind the UK's departure from the European Union was the British media's use of persuasive communication strategies. Media outlets employed a range of tools to influence public opinion. Both pro-Leave and pro-Remain newspapers acted as powerful agents of persuasion.. These pro-Leave tabloids, known for their forceful and emotionally charged language, reached a much larger audience than broadsheet papers. Consequently, their backing of the Leave campaign had a significant influence on the referendum result. A central rhetorical tool used by these tabloids was a strong tone of Euroscepticism.

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